

Heterogeneity of Iron Oxide and Its Catalytic Activity

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Ferric oxide, besides resembling chromia in structure, exhibits semiconducting properties similar to it. Since the oxidation states of iron are less numerous than chromium, it was considered interesting to extend some of the studies made on chromia to iron oxide.

EXPERIMENTAL

The catalyst was prepared by the dehydration of ferric hydroxide precipitated from a ferric chloride solution using ammonia¹. Catalysts of different compositions were obtained by reducing the ferric oxide in pure hydrogen for various lengths of time. The ferrous and ferric contents were determined by titration against dichromate². Chromatographically pure isopropanol was reacted over equal weights of the iron oxide (1.7 g) at 435° at a flow rate of 17.5 ml/hr in a reactor kept slightly inclined. The products were analysed by vapour phase chromatography.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Some typical results obtained on iron oxide reduced for different lengths of time are given in Table I. It is seen that the dehydrogenation activity goes through a maximum with progressive reduction of the iron oxide. The enhanced activities correspond to a catalyst comprising only of ferric oxide and ferrous oxide. In all cases where metallic iron is present, the activity is poor. It may be suggested that the interface of the two oxides has an activity superior to that of pure ferric oxide, ferrous oxide or iron metal, or that magnetite which is considerably more active than ferric oxide³ is formed as an intermediate. Several

TABLE I

The activity of iron oxide reduced for various times for the dehydration and dehydrogenation of isopropanol

Time of reduction hrs.	Composition of catalyst		Moles of product/100 moles of isopropanol	
	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Acetone	Water
0	—	99.0	38.9	2.8
1	9.9	90.4	52.1	1.3
2	70.1	34.4	40.7	1.2
4	89.2	11.5	29.9	1.2

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workers^{4,5,6} have reported the enhancement of catalytic activity due to the formation or the presence of interfaces. Alternatively, the semiconducting nature of the catalyst might have changed on treatment with hydrogen, to increase its activity. Iron metal taken alone has only a very feeble dehydrogenating activity.

It was noticed that all the samples treated with hydrogen were strongly attracted by a magnet, presumably due to formation of magnetite or gamma ferric oxide⁷. The original ferric oxide prepared was not magnetic.

In all the cases where isopropanol was used, propylene, propane and water were detected in the products. The propane could result either from a direct reduction of the alcohol or by the hydrogenation of the propylene formed by dehydration of the alcohol. Unlike in the case of chromia⁸, when propylene-hydrogen mixtures were passed over iron oxide, propane was formed. Acetone-hydrogen mixtures yielded propylene and propane, but no propanol. This result does not permit arriving at any conclusion as to whether the propane is formed directly from isopropanol or through propylene.

By reacting an olefin or a carbonyl compound with an alcohol that can be dehydrogenated over ferric oxide, it should be possible to effect a hydrogen transfer to the former. A mixture of benzyl alcohol and acetone when passed over iron oxide gave rise to isopropanol and even toluene. The formation of toluene suggests that propane may also form from isopropanol by a direct reduction.

Unlike chromia, iron oxide undergoes extensive reduction during the reaction of isopropanol. So, when the steady state is reached, the catalyst will have changed in composition. In spite of a similarity in structure between iron oxide and chromia their catalytic behaviour is quite different. On iron oxide, it would appear that the seat of catalytic activity is the interface between oxides of iron when the metal atom is present in different oxidation states. The changes in structure, formation of new phases and modification in the semiconducting properties of the catalyst are presently under investigation.

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